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NOVEL STRATEGY FOR HEAD MOVEMENT BASED DRIVING ASSISTANCE FOR WHEELCHAIR WITH GSM HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM

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Abstract:

People with disabilities due to serious spinal cord injuries cannot move the conventional type hand powered wheelchair without external assistance. Here we are developing a head movement based control system for wheelchairs. Here the head posture is tracked by an accelerometer, which directs the motor driver, using a microcontroller system. We provide ultrasonic sensors to avoid accidents. A GSM health monitoring system is also attached along this.

Keywords— *Wheelchair, Accelerometer, Ultrasonic sensors, Motor driver, GSM module*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobility is one of the most important needs in human life. It plays a major role in our self esteem. In the case of Quadriplegics, a situation in which people lose their motion due to damage in spinal cord. Our project introduces a wheelchair system, which is controlled by the head movement. The patient suffering from serious spinal cord injuries can move without any assistance from other people. The head position is tracked by an accelerometer that helps to direct the wheelchair. A health monitoring system is also attached to the unit, which includes heart beat and temperature monitoring. In case of any change in the reference, the system will inform to the hospital and nearest persons with the help of a GSM module.

II. BASIC WORKING

The posture of the head is tracked by an accelerometer, which works on MEMS technology. The accelerometer is fitted on a hat that the disabled person will wear. Accelerometer detects the tilting action of head and gives forward, backward, left and right movements of the wheelchair. Wheelchair stops when the head is in

normal position. We place the tilt sensors on the top of patients head so that the accelerometer can produce proper signals. This is very helpful for the patients with severe spine injuries. The existing joystick wheelchairs are too expensive and can only be controlled by hand movement. This project can be mounted on that kind of joystick wheelchairs, with a low cost. There are two ultrasonic sensors for detecting obstacles. Here we are using PING))) ultrasonic distance sensors. There are two cylindrical structures in PING))) sensors, one is transmitting end and other is receiving end. The transmitting end transmits ultrasonic signals and gets reflected at the obstacles. The sensor measures the time required for the echo return and returns its value to the microcontroller as a variable width pulse. This ultrasonic sensor provides precise measurements of non-contact distance within 2 cm to 3 m. One sensor is mounted on the front and other on back of the wheelchair to detect obstacles. Whenever sensors detect an obstacle, the PING))) ultrasonic distance sensors transmit the signals to microcontroller and break the wheelchair. Here we are using a 12V, 7Ah lead acid battery for both microcontroller and the driving system.

The 12V is converted to 5V using IC7405 for the microcontroller power input. The microcontroller is the brain of the whole system. Signals from accelerometer & ultrasonic sensors give input to the microcontroller. We've developed a simple program for getting desired output from the microcontroller. The microcontroller gives input to the driver circuit. Driver circuit consists of six relays. Here we have used an electromechanical relay. Each motor is controlled by two relays. This provides forward and reverse motion of each motor. So that we can move the wheelchair forward, backward, right and left directions. The relays are excited directly by the battery. The relay consists of three positions-common, normally open (NO) and normally closed (NC).

Whenever a switching is required the relays alter its position between NC and NO, thereby reversing polarity and changing the direction of motion of the motor. The motor used in our project is a 12V, 120 W, geared dc motor. The construction is similar to that of the normal dc motor but in addition a gearbox is attached to the shaft of the motor. The primary aim of the gearbox (reduction gears) is to regulate the speed of the motor below its normal speed of rotation. Since angular velocity is decreased the net Torque is increased. Thus the wheelchair can accommodate heavier weights of patients. There is a heart monitoring system also implemented here, so whenever the patient heart beat gone above or below the reference, an emergency message will be delivered to the nearest person and the hospital. We have maintained every aspects of safety while designing the wheelchair and the whole unit is user friendly. Moreover the unit can be implemented in any existing wheelchairs.

III. BLOCK DIAGRAM

IV. HARDWARE SYSTEM

1. Microcontroller AT mega 328P:

The high-performance Atmel Pico Power 8-bit AVR RISC-based microcontroller combines 32KB ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 1024B EEPROM, 2KB SRAM, 23 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, three flexible timer/counters with compare modes, internal and external interrupts, serial programmable USART, a byte-oriented 2-wire serial interface, SPI serial port, a 6-channel 10-bit A/D converter (8-channels in TQFP and QFN/MLF packages), programmable watchdog timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power saving modes. The device operates between 1.8-5.5 volts. By executing powerful instructions in a single clock cycle, the device achieves throughputs approaching 1 MIPS per MHz, balancing power consumption and processing speed.

2. Accelerometer

An accelerometer is an electro mechanical device that measures acceleration forces. Here we find out the angle the device is tilted at with respect to the earth. This is done by sensing the amount of dynamic acceleration. Here we use Toshan ADXL 335 Accelerometer

3. Sensor

Ultrasonic sensors are used to detect objects and distances. Utilize the properties of sound. Objects and distances are determined precisely and with excellent background suppression and immunity to many types of foreign objects in the environment. The output used – switching, analog, or both – is determined on the basis of your application require,

V. FLOW CHART

VI. ADVANTAGES

- Our project help physically handicapped persons for their independent movement. It will able to navigate in their indoor and outdoor environment.
- Reduction in dependence of the disabled on care givers and other family members and to promote feelings of self-reliance.It promotes self confidence in patients.
- It is considerably low in cost.
- Assistance to civilians suffering grievous injuries that led them to be wheel chair bound for mobility.

VII. CONCLUSION

We developed an automated driving assistance for wheelchair. This helps physically disabled persons for their independent movement. This control system provides an intelligent wheelchair system . So, this is

an extremely useful system for user having restricted limb movements caused by some diseases such as Parkinson's diseases and quadriplegics.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

Firstly, we would like to implement a wireless unit into the wheelchair comprising of a receiver section, transmitter section and antenna. These wiring arrangements can be reduced and wireless operation can be implemented. Then there is also a proposal for implementation of a health monitoring system in our project. Finally we are planning to use eye retina optical sensors to control the wheelchair motion in different direction. Researchers are in its full swing on

development of wheelchair using human nervous system.

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